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Abstract: Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) is a complex infectious disease caused by several bacterial and viral pathogens, including bovine viral diarrhea virus (BVDV) and bovine herpesvirus-1 (BHV-1). Both viruses are important cattle pathogens that induce a broad immunosuppression on cell-mediated immune response on its own. To our knowledge, no studies have been made in cattle comparing the leukocyte population counts, including systemic changes in lymphocyte subpopulations, during dual viral respiratory infections in calves. Our aim was to evaluate quantitative changes in immunocompetent cells in healthy calves and calves with subclinical bovine viral diarrhea (BVD), both inoculated with BHV-1. Neutrophils and lymphocyte exhibited changes in behaviour which can contribute to the immunosuppression of BVDV, thus accounting for some of the inter-group differences. Unlike the others lymphocyte subpopulations studied, CD8+ T cell displayed an early depletion in BVDV inoculated calves that can promote greater dissemination of BHV-1 aggravating the course of the disease.

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Effect of infection with BHV-1 on peripheral blood leukocytes and lymphocyte subpopulations in calves with subclinical BVD

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25 **Abstract**

26 Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) is a complex infectious disease caused by
27 several bacterial and viral pathogens, including bovine viral diarrhea virus (BVDV)
28 and bovine herpesvirus-1 (BHV-1). Both viruses are important cattle pathogens that
29 induce a broad immunosuppression on cell-mediated immune response on its own.
30 To our knowledge, no studies have been made in cattle comparing the leukocyte
31 population counts, including systemic changes in lymphocyte subpopulations, during
32 dual viral respiratory infections in calves. Our aim was to evaluate quantitative
33 changes in immunocompetent cells in healthy calves and calves with subclinical
34 bovine viral diarrhea (BVD), both inoculated with BHV-1. Neutrophils and
35 lymphocyte exhibited changes in behaviour which can contribute to the
36 immunosuppression of BVDV, thus accounting for some of the inter-group
37 differences. Unlike the others lymphocyte subpopulations studied, CD8+ T cell
38 displayed an early depletion in BVDV inoculated calves that can promote greater
39 dissemination of BHV-1 aggravating the course of the disease.

40

41 **Keywords**

42 Bovine respiratory disease complex; bovine viral diarrhea virus; bovine herpesvirus
43 type 1; immune response; flow cytometry; cell subsets

44

45 **Abbreviations**

46	BHV-1	bovine herpesvirus type 1
47	BHV-1.1	bovine herpesvirus type 1 and subtype 1
48	BVD	Bovine viral diarrhea
49	BRD	Bovine respiratory disease

50	BVDV	bovine viral diarrhea virus
51	BHV1 group	group of animals inoculated only with BHV-1.1
52	BVDV/BHV1 group	group of animals inoculated with BVDV and BHV-1.1
53	TCID ₅₀	tissue culture infective dose 50%
54	dpi	days post-inoculation with BHV-1.1
55	hpi	hours post-inoculation with BHV-1.1
56	°C	Celsius grades
57	Rt	room temperature

58

59 **1. Introduction**

60 Bovine respiratory disease (BRD) complex is a major cause of economic loss
61 in the cattle industry, weakening the immune system and making the animal more
62 susceptible to secondary infections. Several infectious agents have been associated
63 with BRD, including bovine viral diarrhea virus (BVDV) and bovine herpesvirus-1
64 (BHV-1). Frequently, severe respiratory tract disease in cattle is associated with
65 concurrent infections of these pathogens (Srikumaran et al., 2007). Although it is
66 known that both viruses can colonize the respiratory tract on its own, their
67 participation in the BRD is mainly due to their enhancer role in mixed infections
68 derived from their significant immunosuppressive effect (Potgieter et al., 1984;
69 Castrucci et al., 1992; Kelling, 2007).

70 The changes related to the immunosuppressive action of BVDV and BHV-1
71 include a transient leucopenia in calves characterized by lymphopenia (Griebel et al.,
72 1987-1988; Müller-Doblies et al., 2004; Pedrera et al., 2009a,b; Risalde et al., 2011b;
73 Raya et al., 2011) with decreases in absolute numbers of B lymphocytes (Bolin et al.,
74 1985; Brewoo et al., 2007), T lymphocytes, mainly both CD4+ and CD8+, and $\gamma\delta$ to

75 a lesser extent (Bolin et al., 1985; Griebel et al., 1987-1988; Winkler et al., 1999;
76 Archambault et al., 2000; Chase et al., 2004), as well as monocytopenia (Glew et al.,
77 2003; Van Drunen Little-van den Hurt, 2007; Pedrera et al., 2009b; Raya et al.,
78 2011) and neutropenia (Filion et al., 1983; Chase et al., 2004; Pedrera et al., 2009a,b;
79 Raya et al., 2011), with impairment of function in monocytes, neutrophils and
80 lymphocytes (Filion et al., 1983; Griebel et al., 1987-1988; Brown et al., 1991;
81 Potgieter, 1995; Tikoo et al., 1995; Glew et al., 2003; Chase et al., 2004). It is known
82 that the cell-mediated immune response plays a key role in countering infection both
83 in BVDV (Howard et al., 1992) and in BHV-1 (Babiuk et al., 1996; Van Drunen
84 Littel-van den Hurk, 2007), since the humoral response is not sufficient to eliminate
85 infected cells.

86 However, to our knowledge, no studies have been made comparing the
87 leukocyte populations, including changes in lymphocyte subpopulations, during dual
88 BVDV and BHV-1 viral respiratory infections in peripheral blood of calves. Parallel
89 studies on kinetics of the cellular response may give valuable information for the
90 understanding of the cell-mediated immune response during co-infections with these
91 viral agents in BRD.

92 The aim of this study was to deepen in the systemic consequences after the
93 immunosuppression associated to an acute BVDV infection, especially the
94 exacerbate effect developed in co-infections with BHV-1 in cattle, such as has been
95 described on histopathological studies (Potgieter et al., 1984; Castrucci et al., 1992).
96 Therefore, we examine systemic changes in leukocyte counts and lymphocyte
97 subpopulations appeared in apparently recovery calves of an experimental bovine
98 viral diarrhea (BVD) and in healthy calves, both challenged with BHV-1.1.

99

100 **2. Materials and methods**

101 *2.1. Experimental procedure*

102 A detailed description of the experimental procedure is given in Risalde et al.
103 (2011b). In brief, thirty male Friesian calves (8-9 months old) were housed in the
104 Animal Experimental Centre of Cordoba University and had an adjustment period of
105 one week before the experiment started, being controlled daily for clinical signs of
106 disease. At the beginning of the experiment, the calves were randomly assigned to
107 three different groups called according to the inoculation they were exposed to.
108 Fourteen calves belonged to the BVDV/BHV1 group, twelve calves to the BHV1
109 group and four belonged to the negative control group.

110 The animals of BVDV/BHV1 group were infected by intranasal inoculation
111 with 10 ml (5ml per nostril) of a suspension containing 10^5 tissue culture infective
112 dose 50% (TCID₅₀)/ml of non-cytopathic BVDV genotype-1 strain 7443. Twelve
113 days later, when the calves did not show neither clinical signs nor viremia against
114 BVDV, the animals of both BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups were challenged
115 receiving an intranasal inoculation with a total of 2 ml (1ml per nostril) containing
116 10^7 TCID₅₀ of BHV-1 subtype 1 (BHV-1.1) virulent strain Iowa. The animals of the
117 negative control group received 1 ml of tissue culture fluid free of viruses in each
118 nostril. Clinical examinations were performed daily and EDTA blood samples were
119 taken at 0, 6, 12 and 18 hours post-inoculation with BHV-1.1 (hpi), 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9
120 and 14 dpi days post-inoculation with BHV-1.1 (dpi).

121

122 *2.2. Blood leukocyte counts*

123 Total and differential leukocyte counts were done on EDTA-blood samples
124 by electronic counting using a Cell-Dyn 3700 Hematology Analyzer (Abbott
125 Diagnostics, Abbott Laboratories, Abbott Park, IL, USA).

126

127 *2.3. Immunolabelling of lymphocyte differentiation antigens*

128 A panel of primary monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) (VRMD, Pullman, WA)
129 specific for bovine CD4+ T cells (CACT138A), CD8+ T cells (CACT80C), B cells
130 (BAQ44A) and $\gamma\delta$ T cells (CACTB6A) were used to examine lymphocyte subsets.
131 FITC conjugate goat anti-mouse IgM (μ -chain specific) (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis,
132 Missouri, USA) and R-phycoerythrin conjugate goat anti-mouse IgG₁ (Invitrogen,
133 San Diego, CA) were used as secondary Ab. Fresh EDTA blood samples were
134 collected and stored at room temperature (Rt), performing the surface labelling
135 within 1 hour after blood extraction, as follows. 100 μ l of whole blood diluted 1:1
136 with PBS was incubated with 1 μ l of each primary mAb enumerated above.
137 Following 30 min of incubation at 4°C in the dark, the cells were washed with 2 ml
138 of PBS. Next, 200 μ l of secondary Ab diluted 1:500 with PBS were added and the
139 cells were incubated for 30 min at 4°C in the dark. After labelling, erythrocytes were
140 lysed, using 2 ml of lysing solution (FACS Lysing Solution 10X Concentrate, Becton
141 Dickinson, San José, CA, USA) for 10 min at Rt. The lysing process was stopped by
142 adding 2 ml of PBS. Finally, the cells were fixed adding 200 μ l of formaldehyde
143 buffered solution (CellFix 10X Concentrate, Becton Dickinson, San José, CA, USA)
144 to each sample and were stored at 4°C in the dark until flow cytometric analysis.

145

146 *2.4. Flow cytometric analysis of lymphocyte subpopulations*

147 The absolute number of each lymphocyte subpopulation reactive with each
148 mAb was calculated using the total lymphocyte number and the proportion of the
149 subpopulation given at the flow cytometric analysis at each time point. Indirect
150 immunofluorescent stained cells were analyzed using a FACScan Flow Cytometer
151 (Becton Dickinson Immunochemistry Systems, San José, Puerto Rico). The software
152 used for data collection and analyses was CELLQuest (Becton Dickinson, San José,
153 CA, USA). Twenty thousand events were collected from each sample. The following
154 parameters were collected: forward light scatter (FSC), side light scatter (SSC), FITC
155 fluorescence (FL1) and PE fluorescence (FL2). Lymphocytes were differentiated by
156 their size (FSC) and granularity (SSC), and further evaluated for lymphocyte
157 subpopulation by FL1 and FL2. The proportions of lymphocytes positive for each of
158 the mAb were determined after subtraction of the corresponding control.

159

160 *2.5. Statistical analyses*

161 The values of total and differential leukocyte counts and absolute number of
162 each lymphocyte subpopulation were assessed to calculate mean \pm standard error.
163 Duncan's Multiple Range Test was performed for BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups
164 to analyze significant differences of the values in each inoculated group at various
165 time points (*). *P* values < 0.05 were considered significant. Non-paired Student's *t*-
166 test was used to determine differences between both BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1
167 groups at the same time point (**). *P* values < 0.05 were considered significant.
168 Statistical analysis software SAS version 9.1 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA)
169 was used for data analysis.

170

171 **3. Results**

172

173 *3.1. Blood leukocyte count*

174 In the BVDV/BHV1 group, the total leukocyte count (Figure 1) starts with
175 significantly lower levels than BHV1 group and stayed in this way until 2 dpi. From
176 this day, a significant increase in total cell count was observed, peaking at 5 dpi.
177 Thereafter, the cell count decreased quickly until reach lowest levels at 9 dpi for this
178 group, recovering values close to pre-inoculation levels the last day. However, in the
179 BHV1 group a minor transient increase in leukocyte number lasted for 2 days after
180 BHV-1.1 inoculation, which was followed by leucopenia between 4 and 9 dpi,
181 remaining lower for the rest of the study compared with pre-inoculation values.

182 Parallel to leukocytes profile, the neutrophil count (Figure 1) was
183 significantly different between both BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups before BHV-1
184 inoculation (0 dpi) and stayed until 2 dpi. In the BVDV/BHV1 group, after a slight
185 initial increase at 12 hpi, the neutrophils had a significantly pronounced peak at 4 and
186 5 dpi. After that, the cell count decreased quickly reaching the lowest level at 9 dpi,
187 recovering the initial values on last day of the study. In the BHV1 group, after BHV-
188 1 inoculation the neutrophil counts had a slight increase at 12 hpi and levelled out
189 until the 2 dpi. However, from this day onward the neutrophil number underwent a
190 significant drop at 4 dpi and remaining with similar low values until the end of the
191 study.

192 In general, the dynamic of the lymphocyte population (Figure 2) was
193 essentially the same in both BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups after BHV-1.1
194 inoculation but with some differences. There are not significant differences in pre-
195 inoculation levels between both inoculated groups. However, in the BVDV/BHV1
196 group, after a non significant slight increase at 6 hpi, the lymphocyte count had a

197 drop from 1 dpi, which was significantly more pronounced at 4 dpi, recovering
198 values close to pre-inoculation towards the last days of the study. In the BHV1
199 group, the lymphocyte count decreased from BHV-1 inoculation and, although
200 fluctuated somewhat, stayed low during the whole study period, reaching the lowest
201 value on 5 dpi.

202 The kinetics of the monocytes is shown in Figure 2. In the BVDV/BHV1
203 group, the monocyte count did not change throughout the study. However, in the
204 BHV1 group, the profile fluctuated somewhat, showing a descent between 2-4 dpi
205 remaining at low levels until 9 dpi and overcoming from that time on the initial
206 values at last day of the study.

207 In the negative control group, the total leukocyte count and the numbers of
208 neutrophils, lymphocytes and monocytes (Figures 1-2) did not change throughout the
209 study.

210

211 *3.2. Lymphocyte subpopulations*

212 In the BVDV/BHV1 group, the profile of the CD4+ and CD8+ kinetics
213 (Figure 3) were essentially the same. In both lymphocyte subsets the levels decreased
214 gradually from 1 to 4 dpi, being significantly the lower values of the study at this
215 time point. Then the CD4+ and CD8+ cell numbers increased at 9 dpi, remaining
216 close to pre-inoculation levels towards the end of the study.

217 In the BHV1 group, the CD4+ (Figure 3) values suffered a descent at 12 hpi
218 and after a slight increase, levels dropped again at 4 dpi reaching the lowest values
219 during the whole study period. After a short recovery at 7 dpi, the CD4+ values
220 dropped and stayed lower than pre-inoculation levels during the rest of the study. The
221 CD8+ subset had significant differences compared with BVDV/BHV1 group during

222 the first 18 hpi. In fact, the CD8⁺ subset remained with values close to pre-
223 inoculation until this time point, and then the cell number showed a significant
224 decrease and reached the lowest level at 4 dpi. Then the cell number increased
225 transiently at 7 dpi, but the values remained low for the rest of the study compared
226 with the pre-inoculation levels.

227 Unlike the others lymphocyte subpopulations studied, the $\gamma\delta$ T subpopulation
228 (Figure 4) showed pre-inoculation values significantly different between both
229 inoculated groups, being much higher in the BVDV/BHV1 group. However, from 12
230 hpi, the dynamics in the BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups were essentially the same
231 where the values fluctuated somewhat for the rest of the study and had not significant
232 differences among time points.

233 The B lymphocyte subset (Figure 4) presented a parallel profile in both
234 BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups characterized by a significant abrupt decrease from
235 1 dpi, dropping throughout the whole study period. From that time onward, the level
236 of B cell counts in the BVDV/BHV1 group stayed mainly below BHV1 group values
237 until the end of the study. Although in the BHV1 group was observed a transient
238 increase on 9 dpi, it was followed by values close to zero at the last day.

239 The lymphocyte subpopulations analysed in the negative control group
240 appeared without changes until the end of the experiment (Figures 3-4).

241

242 **4. Discussion**

243 This study evaluated quantitative changes in leukocytes and circulating
244 lymphocyte subpopulations in healthy calves and calves with subclinical BVD, both
245 inoculated with BHV-1, with a view to ascertaining the effect of BVDV on the
246 response of these immunocompetent cells and on the development of BRD involving

247 a BHV-1 infection. Inter-group differences in the severity of clinical symptoms were
248 accompanied by differences in the viremia (Risalde et al., 2011b). Whilst leukocyte
249 populations such as monocytes displayed no significant alteration, lymphocyte
250 subpopulations and neutrophils exhibited changes in behaviour which probably
251 enhanced the immunosuppressive effect of BVDV, thus accounting for some of the
252 inter-group differences observed.

253 In BVDV-infected calves, leukocyte numbers are reported to return to
254 normal between 7 and 12 dpi (Wilhelmsen et al., 1990; Archambault et al., 2000;
255 Pedrera et al., 2009a,b). Here, at 0 dpi, i.e., 12 dpi BVDV calves inoculated with
256 BVDV displayed significantly lower leukocyte levels than healthy calves, though
257 neither viremia nor clinical symptoms were apparent (Risalde et al., 2011b); this
258 suggested a difference in status prior to inoculation of the secondary pathogen BHV-
259 1. Moreover, analysis of the various leukocyte populations indicated that this
260 difference was due mainly to a significant lower number of neutrophils, which
261 constitute the first line of cellular defence against invading pathogens (Paape et al.,
262 2003). Since lymphocytes and monocyte-macrophages are the primary target cells
263 for BVDV replication (Bruschke et al., 1998; Glew et al., 2003; Risalde et al.,
264 2011a), it was somewhat surprising that initial levels of these cell populations should
265 be similar in healthy and BVDV-infected calves prior to inoculation with BHV-1.

266 Following inoculation with BHV-1, a significant difference in leukocyte
267 counts was observed between the BVDV/BHV1 and BHV1 groups, mainly affecting
268 neutrophils and, to a lesser extent, lymphocytes and monocytes. BHV1 is known to
269 induce a state of leukopenia associated with lymphopenia (Griebel et al., 1987,
270 1988), neutropenia (Filion et al., 1983) and monocytopenia (Van Drunen Littel-van
271 den Hurk, 2007). In the BHV1 group, leukocyte depletion was noted from 4 dpi.

272 Paradoxically, calves in the BVDV/BHV1 group – despite to present a lower
273 leukocyte number, due probably to immunodepression induced by BVDV
274 inoculation (Chase et al., 2004; Pedrera et al., 2009b) – displayed leukocytosis
275 resulting from an increase in circulating neutrophils, with no significant change in
276 monocyte numbers even though lymphopenia was more severe than in the BHV1
277 group. The neutropenia prompted by BHV-1 in the previously healthy group
278 contrasted with the neutrophilia observed in the BVDV/BHV1 group which had
279 initially exhibited BVDV-induced neutropenia. These findings could be indicating
280 the continuing ability of calves with BVDV to react to infection by recruiting
281 neutrophils. However, this response may be rendered less effective due to the
282 inhibitory action of BVDV on neutrophil transendothelial migration (Brown et al.,
283 1991; Potgieter, 1995; Glew et al., 2003). BVDV-induced sequestration of peripheral
284 blood neutrophils would hinder their migration to the infection site and also
285 ultimately give rise to neutrophilia; this effect may be enhanced by BHV-1 (Filion et
286 al., 1983). However, the likelihood that BVDV might inhibit neutrophil migration is
287 weakened by the fact that neutrophilia coincided here with increased evidence of
288 inflammatory signs (Risalde et al., 2011b).

289 BHV-1 viremia of varying duration has been reported in infection involving
290 highly-virulent strains, and also in very young animals (Castrucci et al., 1992;
291 Kaashoek et al., 1996). On the other hand, BHV-1 replication has been confined to
292 the surface of airway mucosae in animals over 3 months old (van Drunen Littel-van
293 den Hurk, 2007). In calves with around 9 month-old, BHV-1.1 was not detected from
294 blood in calves infected only with BHV-1.1, in contrast to calves co-infected with
295 BVDV and BHV-1.1 in which BHV-1.1 was confirmed from 4 dpi until the end of
296 the study; that it could be indicating a failure of anti-BHV1 mechanisms in calves

297 inoculated with BVDV. This impairment of antiviral mechanisms appears to have
298 induced a reactivation of BVDV in these animals, since at the time of BHV-1
299 inoculation calves in the co-infected BVDV/BHV1 calves did not exhibit BVDV
300 viremia, and after BHV-1.1 inoculation, BVDV reappeared (Risalde et al., 2011b). In
301 fact, previous works report transitory viremia until 12-14 dpi in BVD (Wilhelmsen et
302 al., 1990; Collen et al., 2002; Brackenbury et al., 2003; Kelling, 2007; Pedrera et al.,
303 2009b). A key role in the impairment of antiviral capacity may be played by
304 circulating T lymphocyte subpopulations (CD4+, CD8+ and $\gamma\delta$) and B cells,
305 involved among others in the cell-mediated immune response, which are known to be
306 capable of interacting with infected cells (Srikumaran et al., 2007).

307 Analysis of lymphocyte subpopulations showed that CD4+ T cell levels were
308 similar in both groups prior to inoculation with BHV-1, reflecting normal values in
309 contrast to the characteristic CD4+ T cell depletion induced by BVDV (Howard et
310 al., 1992; Collen et al., 2002). Following inoculation with BHV-1, both groups
311 displayed a slight decline in CD4+ T cell numbers from 6 hpi, being the lowest
312 counts recorded at 4 dpi. Despite this decline, numbers in both groups had returned to
313 normal levels by the end of the study. This would suggest that BVDV does not
314 impair the regenerative capacity of circulating CD4+ T cells, changes in CD4+
315 lymphocyte levels in response to BHV-1 being similar in healthy calves and calves
316 with subclinical BVD. The similarity in CD4+ lymphocyte kinetics indicates that the
317 changes observed were induced probably by BHV-1, which can infect specifically
318 this subpopulation (Babiuk et al., 1996; Winkler et al., 1999; Van Drunen Littel-van
319 den Hurk, 2007).

320 Although CD8+ T cell levels were similar prior to BHV-1 inoculation,
321 significant differences in cell counts between the BVDV/BHV1 group and the BHV1

322 group were apparent from 6 hpi. The constant decline observed in the BVDV/BHV1
323 group was not seen in the BHV1 group, suggesting that it was attributable not to
324 infection of these cells by BHV-1 but rather to BVDV-induced migration of CD8+ T
325 cells to the infection site (Winkler et al., 1999; Van Drunen Littel-van den Hurk,
326 2007). Between 1 and 7 dpi, CD8+ T cell counts behaved in a similar manner in the
327 two groups, the most marked depletion being observed at 4 dpi. The decline in
328 numbers was more pronounced in the BVDV/BHV1 group, where the virus was not
329 contained, being BHV-1 detected in the blood of BVDV/BHV1 calves from 4 dpi
330 (Risalde et al., 2011b). These results may be indicate an impairment of the cytotoxic
331 action of CD8+ T cells as a defence against the cell-to-cell dissemination
332 characteristic of BHV-1 prior to blood-borne dissemination (Van Drunen Little-van
333 den Hurt, 2007). CD8+ T cell depletion from the start of the study, together with
334 delayed production of IFN γ compared to healthy calves, would favour the
335 development of BHV-1 viremia as well as the reactivation of BVDV and its
336 persistence in target organs, aggravating the lesions associated with both diseases
337 (Risalde et al., 2011b).

338 Numbers of $\gamma\delta$ lymphocytes were higher in the BVDV/BHV1 group prior to
339 infection with BHV-1. This initial difference might have affected the response to
340 secondary infection, although the systemic role of this lymphocyte subpopulation in
341 countering pathogenic agents has not yet been clearly established. Amadori et al.
342 (1995) note that in BHV-1 infection inhibition of virus replication is among the
343 antiviral activities attributed to circulating $\gamma\delta$ T cells. In the present study, $\gamma\delta$ T cells
344 reached normal levels in the BVDV/BHV1 group at 6 hpi. Thereafter, and
345 throughout the study, kinetics and cell counts remained similar in both groups. This
346 would suggest that, although circulating $\gamma\delta$ T cell levels were initially higher in the

347 BVDV/BHV1 group, these cells did not play a major systemic role in containing
348 BHV-1.1 dissemination, since viremia was detected in this group, but not in the
349 BHV1 group (Risalde et al., 2011b).

350 Reports regarding changes in circulating B lymphocyte counts following
351 BVDV infection vary; some authors have noted a decline (Brewoo et al., 2007),
352 others have observed no effect (Archambault et al., 2000), whilst still others have
353 recorded a transitory increase (Brodersen and Kelling, 1999). BVDV exerts its
354 greatest effect on thymic and follicular B lymphocytes in lymph nodes and Peyer's
355 patches (Brodersen and Kelling, 1999; Pedrera et al., 2009a,b; Raya et al., 2011;
356 Risalde et al., 2011b). Although pre-inoculation counts were similar in both groups,
357 B lymphocyte counts in the BVDV/BHV1 group were lower than in the BHV1 group
358 from 1 dpi onwards, possibly reflecting the reduced ability of depleted lymphoid
359 organs to produce B cells. Brewoo et al. (2007) report that, in addition to prompting a
360 severe reduction in the number of circulating B lymphocytes, BVDV often results in
361 the suppression of the functional activities of these cells. However, in the
362 BVDV/BHV1 group anti-BVDV Ab were detected from 4 dpi BHV1 (i.e. 16 dpi
363 BVDV) (Risalde et al., 2011b), being a delayed response, a finding also reported by
364 other authors (Wilhelmsen et al., 1990; Archambault et al., 2000; Müller-Doblies et
365 al., 2004, Pedrera et al., 2009b), while neutralizing Ab to BHV-1 were detected in
366 both groups from 14 dpi BHV1 (Risalde et al., 2011b); other authors (Kaashoek et
367 al., 1996; OIE, 2010) have noted a BHV-1 specific humoral immune response at
368 around 7-10 dpi. Here, a strong Ab response was observed following inoculation
369 with BHV-1 (Risalde et al., 2011b), suggesting that despite the sharp drop in B cell
370 numbers in both groups, functional capacity was not diminished; similar findings are
371 reported by Filion et al. (1983).

372

373 **5. Conclusion**

374 Developed cell-mediated immune response against BHV-1, in animals
375 previously infected with BVDV, results less effective in containing the spread of
376 virus and clarification of the BHV-1 and BVDV. The failure of the antiviral
377 mechanisms developed against BHV-1 in the calves infected with BVDV could be
378 partially due to the significant changes observed in the CD8+ T lymphocyte
379 subpopulation compared with healthy animals. This coupled with significant
380 numerical changes found in the neutrophil population, may contribute to poor cell-
381 mediated immune response against viral secondary infections with BHV-1, showing
382 the synergy of BVDV and BHV-1 on viremia, but also on clinical symptoms, in the
383 animals of the BVDV/BHV1 group, predisposing to the development of
384 inflammatory processes.

385

386 **Conflict of interest statement**

387 The authors do not have any financial or personal relationships with other
388 people or organizations that could inappropriately influence (bias) their work.

389

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397

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547

548 **Figure captions**

549

550 **Figure 1.** Mean number ($\times 10^9 l^{-1}$) \pm standard error of total leukocyte and neutrophil
551 counts in blood samples from calves experimentally inoculated with bovine
552 herpesvirus-1 (BHV1 group) versus calves inoculated with both bovine viral diarrhea
553 virus and bovine herpesvirus-1 (BVDV/BHV1 group). *Significant differences ($p <$
554 0.05) within each inoculated group at various time points. **Significant differences
555 ($p < 0.05$) between inoculated groups at the same time point. (dpi BHV-1.1, means
556 days post-inoculation with BHV-1.1; 0, include BHV-1.1 pre-inoculation values; h,
557 means hours post-inoculation with BHV-1.1).

558

559 **Figure 2.** Mean number ($\times 10^9 l^{-1}$) \pm standard error of lymphocyte and monocyte
560 counts in blood samples from calves experimentally inoculated with bovine
561 herpesvirus-1 (BHV1 group) versus calves inoculated with both bovine viral diarrhea
562 virus and bovine herpesvirus-1 (BVDV/BHV1 group). *Significant differences ($p <$
563 0.05) within each inoculated group at various time points. **Significant differences
564 ($p < 0.05$) between inoculated groups at the same time point. (dpi BHV-1.1, means

565 days post-inoculation with BHV-1.1; 0, include BHV-1.1 pre-inoculation values; h,
566 means hours post-inoculation with BHV-1.1).

567

568 **Figure 3.** Mean \pm standard error absolute numbers ($\times 10^9 l^{-1}$) of CD4+ and CD8+
569 lymphocytes in blood samples from experimentally inoculated with bovine
570 herpesvirus-1 (BHV1 group) versus calves inoculated with both bovine viral diarrhea
571 virus and bovine herpesvirus-1 (BVDV/BHV1 group). *Significant differences ($p <$
572 0.05) within each inoculated group at various time points. **Significant differences
573 ($p < 0.05$) between inoculated groups at the same time point. (dpi BHV-1.1, means
574 days post-inoculation with BHV-1.1; 0, include BHV-1.1 pre-inoculation values; h,
575 means hours post-inoculation with BHV-1.1).

576

577 **Figure 4.** Mean \pm standard error absolute numbers ($\times 10^9 l^{-1}$) of $\gamma\delta$ and B lymphocytes
578 in blood samples from experimentally inoculated with bovine herpesvirus-1 (BHV1
579 group) versus calves inoculated with both bovine viral diarrhea virus and bovine
580 herpesvirus-1 (BVDV/BHV1 group). *Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) within each
581 inoculated group at various time points. **Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between
582 inoculated groups at the same time point. (dpi BHV-1.1, means days post-inoculation
583 with BHV-1.1; 0, include BHV-1.1 pre-inoculation values; h, means hours post-
584 inoculation with BHV-1.1).

585

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